

THE
ARANEIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA
Part 1 A-C

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THE ARANEIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT (part 1-3)

The family Araneidae has a worldwide distribution with a large diversity of 174 genera and 3128 species. With the large number of specimens sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) several genera have been identified as possibly new records for South Africa. In this guide we discuss 47 genera represented by 105 species that are all listed on the South African National Species List but 16 of these genera represented by 36 species are not listed on the World Spider Catalog for South Africa yet. Only 21 of the species are South African endemics. Of the 105 species 93 (88%) have a wide distribution and is listed as Least Concern and nine are Data Deficient. Only three species are of special concern: *Caerostris tinamaze* Gregorič, 2015 being Vulnerable under the B criterion and the two bolas species *Cladomelea akermani* Hewitt, 1923 and *Cladomelea debeeri* Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004 are listed as Endangered. There are numerous of new species that still need to be described and for only 66 species both sexes are known. It will therefore take time before the exact status of the Araneidae will be known.

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FAMILY ARANEIDAE Clerck, 1757

The family Araneidae has a worldwide distribution with a large diversity of 174 genera and 3128 species. In South Africa the family is represented by 41 genera and 105 species of which 66 species are endemic (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Orb-web Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size varies between genera (3-30 mm). The males are usually smaller and distinct sexual dimorphism occurs. Colour varies from cream to brown to greyish black or brightly coloured; colour allows the spider to blend in with its environment when resting. Carapace: smooth or with numerous protuberances especially in species found on bark; eight eyes in two rows (4:4). Abdomen usually as wide as it is long; usually overhanging the carapace; sometimes covered with protuberances or decorated with patterns. Legs not very long, when at rest they are usually kept close to the body; leg III usually shortest

LIFESTYLE: Most species are nocturnal and procryptic by day, resting with their bodies pressed against the substrate. Orb-web spiders have poor vision and locate their prey by feeling the vibrations and tensions of the web. They wrap their prey with alternating movements of their fourth pair of legs by pulling the silk from the spinnerets and throwing large bands of silk over the prey. The spider hangs head down in the middle of the orb-web or is found in a retreat close by. The web can be either horizontal or vertical. It consists of bridge lines, radii and a circular area, usually made of adhesive threads. The shape, number of radii and position of webs vary between the different genera. Retreat: Some genera construct a tunnel-shaped retreat of silk and plant debris on one side of the web. The spider is then in contact with the web via a signal trip line.

A total of 36 araneid species have been sampled from agroecosystems in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013)), but none of them were sufficiently abundant in any crop to be regarded as an agrobiont. On citrus, four species of araneids were observed to prey on the citrus psylla (Van den Berg et al., 1992), amongst which was an *Araneus* sp. Of the 18 species of araneids collected on cotton, most were rare except for *Neoscona triangula*, *N. blondeli*, *N. subfusca* and *Nemoscolus obscurus*, which were regularly found. Araneids were also the most abundant spiders collected from tomatoes. Araneids were observed preying on *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) moths and larvae, both in the laboratory and in the field (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al., 1999).

TAXONOMY: Several genera have been revised but many genera are still in need of revision.

Argiopinae

Araneinae

Cyrtophorinae

Gasteracanthinae

Nephilinae

Cyrtarachninae

Undescribed spp.

GENUS *ACANTHARACHNE* Tullgren, 1910

The genus *Acantharachne* Tullgren, 1910 is known from Madagascar and the Afrotropical Region from eight species (World Spider Catalog 2020). No species are recorded from South Africa but several have been collected and still need to be described.

COMMON NAMES: Acantharachne Orb-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Acantharachne cornuta* Tullgren, 1910

MORPHOLOGY: Cephalothorax as long as wide; characterized by the strong horn-like tubercles on the cephalic region; differs from tubercles on carapace of *Cladomelea* that are sharply pointed (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2019); carapace high; median eyes are located on a fairly low tubercle; median ocular area wider at the front than at the rear and a little wider than long; lateral eyes widely spaced from the median eyes; clypeus wide and the basal part curved forward. Sternum heart-shaped; posterior tip inserted between the hind legs. Abdomen wider than long; species decorated with humps and horn-like processes. Legs unarmed, and the front legs only slightly longer than the hind legs; legs differ from *Cladomelea*, which has the metatarsi and tarsi I covered with a dense layer of thin, long silky hair.

LIFESTYLE: Nothing is known about the behaviour of *Acantharachne*. Emerit (2000) suggested that the Malagasy species may forage using a bolas, although there are no direct observations supporting the implied hunting strategy.

TAXONOMY: Levi (2003) suggested that when males of *Acantharachne* are found it probably will probably synonymized with *Cladomelea* or *Ordgarius*. Several undescribed species are known from South Africa.

Undescribed spp.

From Wakefield KZN Photos P. Webb

From Kloof Photos A. Saunders

From Kleinmond Photo ASD

From Rhemardo Photos C. Haddad

GENUS *ACUSILAS* Simon, 1895

The genus *Acusilas* described by Simon (1895) contains nine species and is mainly known from Asia, but a single species is recorded from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Rolled Leaf Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Acusilas coccineus* Simon, 1895

MORPHOLOGY: Small to medium sized-spiders (2.50-14.00 mm), males usually much smaller than females. Carapace with narrow cephalic region ; with a prominent groove between thorax and cephalothorax regions in female, absent in males; anterior median eyes closer to anterior lateral eyes than to each other. Abdomen longer than wide, extending beyond the spinnerets. Abdominal folium with four lobes anteriorly (Schmidt & Scharff 2008).

LIFESTYLE: They build regular vertical orb-webs which incorporates a rolled leaf in the centre (Murphy & Murphy 1983).

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Acusilas sp.

Photo N. Bay

Acusilas africanus female Photo E. Klimsa

Acusilas africanus Simon, 1895

COMMON NAME: African Rolled Leaf Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Simon (1895) from Sierra Leone. Although recorded only from six countries, the species is suspected to occur in more African countries. In South Africa, it is recorded from three provinces including two protected areas (EOO=240 932 km², AOO= 24 km², 16-1930 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a web-dweller known to occur in leaf litter in coastal dunes. It builds regular vertical orb-webs that incorporates a rolled leaf in the centre. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Gabon, Sierra Leone, Tanzania. New record: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Farm Wakefield Midlands (-29.28, 29.53). *Limpopo:* Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006) and Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Reviewed by Schmidt & Scharff (2008). Known from both sexes.

Acusilas africanus Photo P. Webb

Acusilas africanus female epigyne

After Schmidt & Scharff (2008).

After Simon (1895)

GENUS *AETHRISCUS* Pocock, 1902

Aethriscus is endemic to Africa, described by Pocock (1902) and known from two species (World Spider Catalog 2020). They are rare spiders and only one species is known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Aethriscus Bird Dropping Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Aethriscus olivaceus* Pocock, 1902

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 7-10 mm, male unknown. Seen from above the body has a triangular shape. Carapace olive-brown; smooth and shiny; with a small tubercle level with the cephalic region constriction; median ocular area narrower in front. Abdomen shiny; olive yellow with darker humps; shape triangular; anterior border straight with 11 sigilla; blunt round humps; posterior area paler. Legs olive-brown, very short and fold around the body.

LIFESTYLE: Little is known about their behaviour. When not active they rest on vegetation and resemble bird droppings (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

TAXONOMY: Not revised, known from two species. Genus resemble species of the genus *Cyrtarachne* Thorell, 1868.

Aethriscus olivaceus

Photo H. de Klerk

Aethriscus sp.

Photo C. de Lange

Aethriscus olivaceus Pocock, 1902

COMMON NAME: Aethriscus Bird Dropping Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of Congo by Pocock (1902). This species is rarely encountered, known only from two African countries. It is however under collected and suspected to occur in more countries on the continent. In South Africa the species is known from five provinces and two protected areas (EOO=281 616 km²; AOO=36 km²; 7-1752 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: A nocturnal orb-web dweller. Little is known about the behaviour of the species. When not active, they rest on vegetation and resemble bird droppings. Sampled from Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011), and from avocado orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: The Democratic Republic of Congo. New record: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (-26.2; 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Shakaskraal (-29.41, 31.26); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (St. Lucia) (-28.00, 32.48); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23). Limpopo: Letaba (-23.82, 30.16). **Mpumalanga:** Hendriksdal Plantation (-25.2, 30.75); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.06).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. It is protected in the following areas: iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Dukuduku Forest Station and St. Lucia. More sampling is needed to determine species identity.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Identification is still problematic. This species is possibly the same as *Cyrtarachne ixioides*.

Aethriscus olivaceus Photo L. Oates

Aethriscus olivaceus Photo ASD

GENUS *AFRACANTHA* Dahl, 1914

Afracantha is a monotypic African genus described by Dahl (1914) from Cameroon (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Spiny-Backed Orb-Web Spiders.

TYPE SPECIES: *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899)

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace broad, with a slight indentation between the cephalic and thoracic region; hump is present behind the eye region; lateral eyes are close together, situated on the carapace border but widely spaced from the median eyes; the posterior median eyes are slightly wider apart than the anterior median eyes. Sternum with posterior tip extends between coxae leg IV. Abdomen from the side high; hard and covered with scattered brown hair; dorsally viewed the anterior edge is rounded, bearing sigilla; two prominent tubercles with sharp tips are present postero laterally and another two on the posterior edge. Legs are short and arranged around the carapace.

LIFESTYLE: They make an orb-web (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021) but little more is known about their behaviour.

TAXONOMY: Not revised, only female known. They are rare spiders.

Desiré Pelsier

Afracantha camerunensis orb-web Photo D. Pelsier

Afracantha camerunensis female dorsal and lateral view Photos D. Pelsier

Afracantha camerunensis (Thorell, 1899)

COMMON NAME: Cameroon Spiny-Backed Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Cameroon by Thorell (1899) as *Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis*. The species is recorded from seven African countries. It is possibly under collected and suspected to occur in the countries in-between. In South Africa the species is known from four provinces and five protected areas (EEO= 137 200 km²; AOO=24 km²; 5-425 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is a web dweller. The web of *Afracantha camerunensis* was spotted in a camp-site in an open area of mown grassland dotted with *Acacia* (now *Vachellia*) trees in the Umgeni Valley (Heron 2017). A spider was suspended in vertically oriented colourless orb-web with a diameter of about 20 cm and supported by a long bridge lines about half a metre below an overhead branch of *Vachellia nilotica*. The orb-web being about 2.0 m from the ground. The species is known to occur in the shrub and tree layer in the Savanna and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ghana, Swaziland, Botswana, Zambia. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-25.73, 32.00); iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Hell's Gate) (-28.0, 32.48); Opathe Nature Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (Macile Piket) (-22.93, 31.02).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Cwebe Nature Reserve; Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Opathe Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); uMkhuze Game Reserve and the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & LeRoy 2003). More sampling needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Monotypic. Known only from female.

Afracantha camerunensis female Photo A. Sander

Afracantha camerunensis female Photos H. Heron

Afracantha camerunensis female abdomen, carapace and epigyne after Levi (1996)

GENUS *ARACHNURA* Vinson, 1863

The genus *Arachnura* is described by Vinson (1863) and it is known from 13 species with only one recorded from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Scorpion-Tail Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Arachnura scorpionoides* Vinson, 1863

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female and male 7-10 mm. Members of this genus have a body with a very long tapering “tail” which can move. The tail extends beyond the spinnerets for a distance of over a third of the abdomen. Colour variation found from brown, cream to bright yellow. Carapace is broad, narrowing anteriorly; eyes are in two rows with posterior median eyes closely spaced. Abdomen is broad with two hornlike projections protruding over the cephalothorax in a V-shape; abdomen tapers into a long tail with soft humps on the tips. Leg II has dark longitudinal stripes over the length; they edge the legs when in resting position (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013, 2020).

LIFESTYLE: They construct a permanent but incomplete orb-web with an open hub. The web is suspended at an angle and has a V-shaped section missing from the top of the web. In autumn/winter the female produces a series of woolly brownish egg sacs, which she strings together in a line from the centre of the web to fill the missing section. The spider takes up position at the bottom of the string in the centre of the web. The female spider curls up her tail over her back like a scorpion if she is threatened. In the web the legs are folded together to form a line (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMY: They are rare spiders and only the one species, *Arachnura scorpionoides* is known from Africa (Cazanove & Begue 2018; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

Arachnura scorpionoides female Photos V vd Walt

Arachnura scorpionoides female Photo A. Saunders

Arachnura scorpionoides Vinson, 1863

COMMON NAME: African Scorpion-Tail Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Madagascar in 1863, based only on a female. The species is recorded from six African countries. It is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in the countries in between. In South Africa it is known from six provinces and >10 protected areas (EOO=759 727 km²; 88 km²: 7-1411 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: *Arachnura scorpionoides* constructs a permanent orb-web with an open hub. The web is suspended on an angle and has a V-shaped section missing from the top of the web. In autumn/ winter the female produces a series of woolly brownish egg sacs which she strings together in a line from the centre of the web to fill the missing section. The spider takes up position at the bottom of the egg string. The female spider curls her tail up over her back like a scorpion if she is disturbed (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020). The front legs are stronger than the rest and kept close to the body when alive. According to literature the male is much smaller than the female, with no tail. Sampled from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011). The species was also sampled from macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2001).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Madagascar, Mauritius, Seychelles and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Island (-28.1, 32.45), Lake Sibayi (-27.35, 32.7), uMkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93). Magoebaskloof Debengeni Falls (-23.87, 30.01). **Mpumalanga:** Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.0); Pilgrims Rest (-24.89, 30.75); Schagen (-25.43, 30.8); Hazyview (-25.03, 31.12).

Arachnura scorpionoides female Photo V vd Walt

Female Photo J. van Zyl

Arachnura scorpionoides females Photos R. van der Lith

Arachnura scorpionoides (continued)

North West: Brits (-25.62, 27.77). **Western Cape:** Bellville (-33.9, 18.63); Stilbaai (-34.36, 21.43); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Table Mountain National Park Newlands Forest (-33.91, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. It is protected in nine areas such as Ndu-mo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006) and the Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Garden Route National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes with well-illustrated drawings. Identification is not problematic (Cazanove & Begue 2018; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

Female epigyne Photo ASD

Female epigyne after Cazanove & Begue (2018)

Arachnura scorpionoides female Photo C. Smit

Female with egg sac Photo C. Smit

Female with eggs Photo R. Dreyer

GENUS *ARANEUS* Clerck, 1757

Araneus is a large genus described by Clerck (1757) and it is represented by 641 species and 14 subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Araneus Hairy Field Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Araneus angulatus* Clerck, 1757

MORPHOLOGY: The carapace is hairy, moderately arched without horny outgrowths. The shape of the fovea varies. The abdomen is soft and hairy; round to oval overlapping the carapace; shoulder humps are present in some. The legs are spiny and tibiae II have ventral spines. They usually have cryptic colouration helping them to blend in with the environment. Some mimic insects. The male palpi have one or two spines on the patella.

LIFESTYLE: They are very common field spiders. They usually do not rest in the middle of the web, at least not in daylight, and stay in retreats made to the side of the web between leaves with a signal thread running to the hub of the web.

TAXONOMY: African fauna is not revised. Embrik Strand described several *Araneus* spp. between 1906 and 1917 but he did not illustrate the species and the descriptions were frequently based on juveniles and exact locality data were seldom provided. Some of the types were also lost during World War II. As it is impossible to recognize the species Nentwig et al. (2020) declared 181 species of Strand to be *nomina dubia*. This includes five *Araneus* species described from South Africa namely: *Araneus caplandensis* (Strand, 1907); *A. haploscapellus* (Strand, 1907); *A. lamperti* (Strand, 1907); *A. meus* (Strand, 1907) and *A. zuluanus* (Strand, 1907).

Araneus nigroquadratus female in web from Noup Photos P. Webb

Araneus sp. female from Wakefield Photo P. Webb

Araneus sp. male from Cape Town Photo P. Webb

Araneus apricus Karsch, 1884

COMMON NAME: Green Pea Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic that was described by Karsch (1884) from São Tomé, based only on a female specimen. It has been collected from seven African countries. This species is possibly under-collected and suspected to occur in the countries in-between. In South Africa the species is known from eight of the nine provinces (EOO=839 170 km²; 216 km²; 7-1556 m a.s.l.) and occurs in more than 10 protected areas. Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: This species is commonly found in the warmer tropical regions. They make an orb-web with a retreat to one side. It is one of the few araneids for which a case study on their bite symptoms exists (Haddad 2002). Sampled from all the floral biomes except the Succulent Karoo (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). The species was also sampled from avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005), citrus and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2001), and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: São Tomé, Yemen, Socotra, Botswana, Namibia, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Swaziland Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park Woody Cape (-33.32, 25.72); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Keurkloof, farm Ferndale (Baviaanskloof) (-33.68, 24.83). **Gauteng:** Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Magaliesburg (-25.99, 27.54); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19); West Pelindaba (-25.8, 27.9). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Melmoth (-28.57, 31.39); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.2); Midlands, Maybole plantation, Richmond (-29.759, 30.258). **Limpopo:** Alma (-24.49; 28.07); Kampersrus (Farm Madrid) (-24.48, 30.83); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylstroom/ Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Acornhoek, Sandringham Nature Reserve (-24.58, 31.1); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Letaba (-23.82, 30.16); Banderlierkop (-23.3, 29.79); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.06); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Tshulu Camp (Venda) (-22.580, 30.809).

Araneus apricus female Photo P. Webb

Araneus apricus male Photo L. Wiese

Araneus apricus female Photo E. Klimsa

Araneus apricus female in retreat Photo J. Munton

Araneus apricus female in web Photo SANSA VM

Araneus apricus (continued)

Mpumalanga: Badplaas (-25.95, 30.56); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.08); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.0); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Olifantsnekdam (-25.8, 27.25); Pelindaba (-25.8, 27.9); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Rhenosterspruit Conservancy (-26.9, 26.38). **Northern Cape:** Hopetown (Farm Suffolk) (-29.58, 24.24); Kuruman (-27.46, 23.43). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Jonkershoek Nature Reserve (-33.98, 18.98); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.87, 22.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. It is protected in >10 protected areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2016) and Blouberg (Muelelwa et al. 2010); Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. New data on the species in South Africa was provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2020).

Araneus apricus female epigyne Photos ASD

Araneus apricus female Photos J. van Zyl

Araneus apricus female from Mooi Nooi Photos P. Webb

A. apricus female Photo K. Geldenhuys

Araneus coccinella Pocock, 1898

COMMON NAME: Coccinella Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic that was described in 1898 from type locality Estcourt in KwaZulu-Natal. A rare species recorded from three provinces including one protected area. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web dweller sampled mainly from three biomes. This species mimics coccinella beetles. The species is rare and little is known about their behaviour. During the long term surveys in Irene specimens were yearly sampled in December and January.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene (Smuts House survey) (-25.89, 28.23); **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Wakefield Farm, Midlands (-29.28, 29.53); Estcourt (-29.1, 29.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Only known from the female. It is easily recognized by the distinct abdominal pattern (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020). This species was previously misidentified in books. Pocock (1989) speculated that this species might not belong to the genus *Araneus*.

Araneus coccinella female from Irene Photos P. Webb

female epigyne

Epigyne after Pocock (1898)

Araneus drygalskii (Strand, 1909)

COMMON NAME: Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described as *Aranea drygalskii* from Simonstown by Strand (1909). The species is known from a single locality in South Africa (EOO= 4 km²; 4 km²; 86 m a.s.l.). Identification of this species is problematic as no drawings were provided and the description is not detailed enough for species identification. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The male was sampled on 21 July 1903 from the Fynbos biome. Nothing known about their behaviour.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Simonstown (-34.19, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Recorded only from type locality. Identification of this species is problematic.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Due to the absence of type material in combination with the lack of recollection and illustration there is a strong arguments to consider this species also as “nomen dubium”.

Araneus fishoekensis (Strand, 1909)

COMMON NAME: Fishoek Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Strand (1909) as *Aranea fishoekensis*, from the type locality Fish Hoek (EOO=4 km²; 4 km²; 50 m a.s.l.). The description is based on a immature specimen. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Identification of the species is problematic, it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: The 3 mm small juvenile specimen was collected 8 July 1903 from the Fynbos biome. Nothing is known about the behaviour.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape*: Fish Hoek (-34.15, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect both sexes and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Due to the absence of type material in combination, description based on a juvenile with lack of recollection and illustration there is a strong arguments to consider the species also as “nomen dubium”.

Araneus gazerti (Strand, 1909)

COMMON NAME: Gazert's Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described from four juveniles by Strand (1909) as *Aranea gazerti* from Fish Hoek, Western Cape (EOO = 4 km²; 4 km²; 50 m a.s.l.). Identification of this species is problematic as juveniles are difficult to identify and no drawings were provided. The status of the species remains obscure, identification is problematic, the species is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Nothing known about the behaviour. The juvenile specimens were sampled on 8 July 1903 from the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Fish Hoek (-34.15, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed. Identification of adults is still problematic.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Due to the absence of type material in combination with description based on a juvenile, with lack of recollection and illustration there is a strong arguments to consider the species as "nomen dubium".

Araneus graemii Pocock, 1900

COMMON NAME: Graem's Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described from Grahamstown by Pocock (1900). The species is known only from the type locality, (EOO = 4 km²; 4 km²; 552 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and range of this taxon for a full assessment to be made. Identification of the species is problematic, and it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web spider known from the Thicket Biome. Nothing more is known about their behaviour.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the male and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Based only on a female. Identification of both sexes is still problematic.

Araneus nigroquadratus Lawrence, 1937

COMMON NAME: Black-spotted Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described from Kosi Bay by Lawrence (1937). The species is known from two African countries (EOO = 806 357 km²; AOO= 164 km²; 0-1842 m a.s.l.). In South Africa it is known from six provinces and >10 protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web spider that makes a large orb-web at night. It sampled from the Savanna (Foord et al. 2011), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Fynbos and Thicket biomes. The species was also sampled from pine plantations and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: East Cape: Cintsa (-32.83, 28.06); Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Great Fish River Wetland Park (-33.48, 27.13); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Komga (-32.58, 27.9); Mkambathi Nature Reserve (-31.27, 30.02); Coega (-33.76, 25.65); Fort Beaufort Mountain View Lodge (-32.78, 26.62); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Prentjiesberg (-31.18, 28.28); Addo National Park (-33.32, 25.72).

Gauteng: Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Drakensberg Mountain Range (-24.62, 30.88); Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Mooirivier (-29.2, 30.00); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Gravelotte (-23.95, 30.57); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Potgietersrus/ Mokopane (-24.17, 29.0); Swartbos Forest (-23.53, 29.59); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Hendriksdal Plantation (-25.2, 30.75); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Goedehoop Forest (-25.093, 30.453); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Western Cape:** Fisherhaven (-34.36, 19.13); Franschoek (-33.89, 19.10); Gouritsmond (Borrelfontein) (-34.34, 21.87); Robben Island (-33.801, 18.357).

Araneus nigroquadratus male Photo E. Klimsa

Araneus nigroquadratus female Photo E. Laubscher

Araneus nigroquadratus female Photo P. Webb

Abdomen and epigyne after Lawrence (1937).

Araneus nigroquadratus Lawrence, 1937 (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Sampled from >10 protected areas such as Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009); Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020) and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from a female specimen. Identification of the male is still problematic.

Araneus nigroquadratus female in web Photo A. Harmsworth

Araneus nigroquadratus female Photo L. Wiese

Araneus strupifer (Simon, 1886)

COMMON NAME: Araneus Hairy Field Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Dakar, Senegal as *Epeira strupifera* by Simon (1886). The species is known from three African countries. It is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in the African countries in-between (EOO= 308504 km²; AOO= 44 km²; 44-1341 m a.s.l.). In South Africa, the species is known from three provinces. Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web spider that makes its web at night. The species is known from the Thicket, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Senegal Tanzania, Kenya and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Fort Grey (-33.19, 27.12). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76); iSimangaliso Wetland park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Mount Edgecombe (-29.68, 31.01); Farm Vergeval, district Ngotsche (-27.35, 31.61); Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve(-23.03, 29.45); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **Northern Cape:** Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003) and Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from female. Identification of male is still problematic.

Araneus strupifer from Benfontein NR Photo ASD

Araneus strupifer from Lhuvhondo NR Photo S. Foord

Araneus strupifer after Pocock (1898)

Araneus tatiana Lessert, 1938

COMMON NAME: Araneus Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lessert 1938 from Ituri, Okondo Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species has also been photographed in South Africa but no more information is available.

LIFESTYLE: Photograph on small plant.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Congo, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Hammanskraal ().

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect live specimens.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Lessert (1938) indicated that he is not sure whether the species belong to *Araneus* Known only from the female.

Habitus and epigyne after Lessert, 1938

Araneus tatiana from Hammanskraal Photo Richard McKibbin

Araneus varus (Kauri, 1950)

COMMON NAME: Grass Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Kauri (1950) as *Larinia vara* from Pietermaritzburg. The species is recorded only from the type locality (EOO= 4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 857 m a.s.l.). Due to sexual dimorphism, it is difficult to recognize the two sexes as belonging to the same species. The species is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web spider that constructs an orb-web in low vegetation and grasses in the Savanna biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Pietermaritzburg Town bush (-29.568, 30.329).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the female and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed Marusik (2017). Known only from the male and identification of female is still problematic.

Araneus varus after Marusik (2017)

Habitat: Ituri: Okondo (1 ♀, type, IX) (A. COLLAR

Araneus undetermined species

Maybe *Araneus detrimmentosus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889) from Woodbush Photo P. Webb

From Kloof Photo P. Webb

From Jeffreysbay Photo L. Wiese

Araneus sp. from Umhlanga Photo P. Webb

Araneus sp. from Wakefield Photo P. Webb

Araneus sp. from Cape Town Photo P. Webb

Araneus sp. from Irene Photo P. Webb

Araneus sp. from Pretoria Photo A. Jones

NEW RECORD

GENUS *ARANIELLA* Chamberlin & Ivie, 1942

Araniella is a genus described by Chamberlin & Ivie (1942) and it is represented by 14 species known mainly from Eurasia, North America, and China (World Spider Catalog 2020). First record of the genus from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Cucumber spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Araniella displicata* (Hentz, 1847)

MORPHOLOGY: Female: Body length both sexes 4.0-6.0 mm. The cephalothorax and legs are yellowish to green; eyes small with posterior median eyes closer to each other than the posterior lateral eyes; lateral eyes close together; median ocular area wider anterior than posterior. The abdomen is light yellow to green in live specimens. Abdomen ovoid, longer than wide; with light green folium, 3 pairs of posterior lateral black spots distinct. Abdominal venter green, yellow or brown stripe laterally. The young become green on reaching maturity. All the abdominal colouration fades in spirit to a uniform dull brown. The legs have no dark rings but are darker distally. The epigyne is small and dark colored with a small short scape.

LIFESTYLE: Sampled with sweep net. Rare species, construct orb-web between shrubs and bushes.

TAXONOMY: The species collected from the Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve is still undetermined. It resembles *Araniella cucurbitina* a species known from Europe, Turkey, Russia (Europe to Far East), Central Asia, China and Iran in having the same number of black spots and general body shape and green colour.

Araniella resemble members of *Prasonica* in body shape and colour but the eye pattern and epigyne differ. In *Prasonica* the epigyne has a very long extended scape.

Araniella cucurbitina from Tswaing Crater Nature Reserve Photos P. Webb

GENUS *ARGIOPE* Audouin, 1826

The genus *Argiope* is known from 87 species and seven species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Garden Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Argiope lobata* (Pallas, 1772)

MORPHOLOGY: These are large araneids with strong sexual dimorphism in shape and size with the males much smaller. Carapace in female is narrower anteriorly, rounded laterally. The sternum is heart-shaped with a wavy margin. The abdomen is oval, often with lateral extensions or lobes, usually brightly coloured with a distinct pattern in different species. Legs are long and slender; I, II and IV are equal, III is shorter. Legs are usually banded (Bjørn 1997).

LIFESTYLE: Orb-webs are made in open grassland areas and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation, in nearly any vegetation sturdy enough to bear their weight. The spider hangs in the hub, head down, throughout the day. The web is accompanied by a barrier web, a network of irregular threads. When disturbed the spider drops or runs off. The web is sometimes decorated with a stabilimentum. The smaller males are frequently found on the edge of the web (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Den Berg 2010; Holm & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010).

TAXONOMY: Species of African region revised by Bjørn (1997).

Argiope australis female Photo L. Oates

Argiope aurocincta Photo C. Haddad

Argiope trifasciata female Photo Allen Jones

Argiope levii female Photo C. Els

Argiope anomalopalpis Bjorn, 1997

COMMON NAME: Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) by Bjørn (1997). The species has been collected only from the DRC and South Africa. This species is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in the countries in-between. In South Africa, the species is recorded from a single locality, Dwesa Nature Reserve in the Eastern Cape (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 7 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species is an orb-web dweller known from the Forest biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Dwesa Nature Reserve (-32.27, 28.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Dwesa Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male, with illustrations. Identification of the female is still problematic.

Male palp after Bjørn (1997).

Argiope aurocincta Pocock, 1898

COMMON NAME: Shield Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Kenya by Pocock (1898). The species has been collected only from four African countries, it may be under collected and is suspected to occur in the African countries in-between. In South Africa the species is known from six provinces (EOO= 614 930 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 29-1513 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes orb-webs in open grassland areas, woodlands and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation. The spider hangs at the hub, head down in its web throughout the day usually with a X shaped stabilimentum. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, South Africa, Tanzania.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9). **Free State:** Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Ndumu Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Opathe Nature Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Phalaborwa, Grietjie Nature Reserve (-24.18, 31.65); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **North West:** Magaliesberg Mountain Sanctuary Park (-25.82, 27.47). **Western Cape:** Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Kenilworth Racecourse Conservation Area (-34.25, 18.5).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Recorded from 12 protected areas such as Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Ndumu Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Opathe Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Bjørn 1997). Known only from the female.

Argiope aurocincta Photo S. Hall

Argiope aurocincta Photo A. Jones

Argiope aurocincta Photo L. de Beer

Argiope aurocincta Photo C. Haddad

After Bjørn (1997).

Argiope australis (Walckenaer, 1805)

COMMON NAME: Common Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Walckenaer (1805) as *Epeira australis*. The species is very common and found throughout Africa (EEO= 1 248 906 km²; AOO= 388 km²; 7-2066 m a.s.l.). In South Africa the species is known from all the provinces. Due to its geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes orb-webs in open grassland areas and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation, in any vegetation sturdy enough to bear their weight. The spider hangs at the hub, head down, throughout the day. The web is frequently decorated with a stabilimentum. After some rain in the Free State at Clocolan an “*Argiope* city” was discovered where between 50-60 spider webs were present in the bushes. It was not common to find so many spiders present just in this one location on the farm, as they are normally found throughout the estate. The spiders were probably attracted to the high numbers of grasshoppers [Orthoptera Acrididae, *Truxalis* sp.] that were found in most webs. Most of the webs were large at least 500 mm, and some even larger; some with stabilimenta others without. The males were in their own webs and only a few were found in females’ webs (Jones 2012; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones 2022)).

The species was sampled from all the floral biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011). It was also collected from crops such as avocado, peach and pistachio orchards, pine plantations and pumpkin fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013). In the past they were frequently found in gardens hence the common name.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Breakfast Vlei (-33.08, 26.95); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Graaff-Reinet (-32.24, 24.53); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Great Fish River Reserve (-33.13, 26.65); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Addo National Park (=-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bothaville (-27.38, 26.62); Clarens (-28.51, 28.43); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Ficksburg (-28.86, 27.86); Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23); Hoopstad (-27.85, 25.93); Tus-sen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13).

Argiope australis male and female
Photo R. Steenkamp

Argiope australis female from Clocolan in web
Photo A. Jones

Argiope australis female from Clocolan in web
Photo A. Jones

Argiope australis (continued)

Gauteng: Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Boksburg (-26.13, 28.15); Hammanskraal (-25.41, 28.27); Irene (Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23); Midrand (-25.95, 28.14); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Sandton, Norscott Koppies (-26.06, 28.07).

KwaZulu-Natal: Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.23, 29.48); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ladysmith (-28.55, 29.76); Ndumu Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Oribi Gorge Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola, (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Sungulwane Game Reserve (-28.87, 31.18); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Thanda Private Game Reserve (-27.87, 32.13); Vryheid (-27.77, 30.79). **Limpopo:** Bandelierskop (-23.31, 29.79); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Ellisras/Lephalale (-23.67, 27.71); Grietjie Nature Reserve (-24.18, 31.65); Louis Trichardt (-23.04, 29.91); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Leopard Creek Reserve (Farm Caledonia) (-23.83, 27.95); Letaba (-23.82, 30.16); Messina/Mussina (-22.34, 30.03); Mooketsi (-23.59, 30.08); Mara (-23.04, 29.66); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Pietersburg/ Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Potgietersrus/ Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Tongwane (-24.22, 29.9); Welgevonden Nature Reserve (-24.39, 27.78). **North-West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Klipvoor Dam (-25.74, 27.84); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Magaliesburg (-25.99, 27.54); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22); Swartruggens (Farm Olivenkloof 373 JP) (-25.54, 26.52). Mpumalanga: Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98); Hectorspruit (-25.43, 31.68); Komatipoort (Farm Sommerreg) (-25.53, 31.82); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Middelburg (-25.76, 29.46); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Schoemanskloof (-25.4, 30.5); Secunda (-26.5, 29.18); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14); Warburton (Farm Weltevreden 68) (-26.2, 30.43). **Northern Cape:** Fraserburg (-31.91, 21.51); Hopetown (Farm Suffolk) (-29.58, 24.24); Kalahari Gemsbok National Park (-25.48, 20.24); Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park (Urikaruus Camp) (-25.78, 20.39); Nieuwoudtville (Hantam Botanical Garden) (-31.34, 19.19); Okiep (-29.59, 17.88); Petrusville (-30.07, 24.66); Tankwa-Karoo National Park (-32.28, 19.82). **Western Cape:** Bainskloof Pass (-33.65, 19.00); Beaufort West (-33.28, 23.22); Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37); Cape of Good Hope Nature Reserve (-34.24, 18.41); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Garden Route (-33.56, 23.04); Grootvadersbos (-34.02, 20.46); Grabouw (-34.14, 19.04); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Karoo Desert National Botanical Garden (-33.61, 19.46); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38); Kommetjie (-34.16, 18.34); Lebanon Forest Station (-34.14, 19.04); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03); Pringle Bay (-34.34, 18.83); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.35, 21.67); Van Rhynsdorp (-31.60, 18.75).

Argiope australis female in web
Photo A. Jones

Argiope australis female in web Photo A Louw

Argiope australis female in web
with prey Photo A. Jones

Epigyne after Bjørn (1997)

Male palp

Argiope australis (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Sampled from more than 30 protected areas including national parks and reserves in all the provinces such as Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Ndumu Game Reserve (Haddad et al 2006) and Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Bjørn 1997). Known from both sexes.

Argiope australis egg laying Photos B. Fourie

Argiope flavipalpis (Lucas, 1858)

COMMON NAME: Banded Argiope Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lucas (1858) as *Epeira flavipalpis*. The species is known from throughout Central, East, Southern Africa and Cape Verde Island. In South Africa the species is known from three provinces including six protected areas (EOO= 39 699 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 47-1077 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide global distribution of the species, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes orb-webs in open grassland areas and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation, in nearly any vegetation sturdy enough to bear their weight. The spider hangs at the hub, head down, throughout the day. McCullum (2012) observed in Durban the species to spun a new webs daily but with the stabilimentum shape differing each day. Webb (2010) observed the species to move with great speed from the front of the web to the back in a flash. This is done through a small slit left in the web. Species sampled from the Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (Letaba Ranch) (-23.82, 30.16); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza Camp) (-25.00, 31.97).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following reserves: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Tembe Elephant Park, Mkuzi Game Reserve, Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Bjørn 1997). Known from both sexes.

Argiope flavipalpis female from garden in Durban
Photo G. McCullum

Argiope flavipalpis female Photo T. Abbott

Argiope flavipalpis juvenile movement on web
Photo P. Webb

Epigyne after Bjørn (1997)

Argiope levii Bjørn, 1997

COMMON NAME: Levi's Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Bjørn (1997) from Tanzania. The species is known from three countries. However it may possibly under collect and is suspected to occur in the countries in-between In South Africa the species is known from three provinces (EOO= 143 419 km²; AOO= 40 km²; 20-1412 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes orb-webs in open grassland areas and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation, in any vegetation sturdy enough to bear their weight. The spider hangs at the hub, head down, throughout the day. The web is sometimes decorated with a stabilimentum. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Lake Sibaya) (-27.35, 32.70); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); St Michael's on Sea (-30.82, 30.38). *Limpopo:* Kampersrus (-24.48, 30.83); Ratombo Forest (-23.06, 30.17); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Haffenden (-23.82, 30.16). *Mpumalanga:* Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following reserves: Lake Sibaya, Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Luvuvhu Nature Reserve, Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016), Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001), Ratombo Forest and Lowveld National Botanical Gardens. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Argiope levii female Kampersrus
Photo P. Webb

After Bjørn (1997)

Argiope levii female Photos C. Els

Argiope lobata (Pallas, 1772)

COMMON NAME: Black-Lobed Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species with a very wide global distribution described in 1772 as *Aranea lobata*. It occurs from the Mediterranean region to China, from Burma to New Caledonia and northern Australia. In Africa the species is known from Morocco and Algeria to Senegal. In South Africa the species is known from eight provinces including >6 protected areas (EOO= 883 650 km²; AOO=72 km²; 63-1780 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic distribution the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make orb-webs in open grassland areas and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation, in nearly any vegetation sturdy enough to bear their weight. The spider hangs in the hub, head down, throughout the day. The species was sampled from the Grassland, Succulent Karoo and Savanna biome (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. (2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: The species occurs from the Mediterranean region to China, from Burma to New Caledonia, northern Australia and Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Wilgerskloof Farm, Bamboesberg, W Sterkstroom (-31.6, 26.37). **Free State:** Clarens (-28.51, 28.43); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **Gauteng:** Krugersdorp / Mogale (-26.09, 27.78); Pyramid (-25.35, 28.37); Irene Gem Village Field (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Mkuzi Game Reserve) (-27.63, 32.25). **Limpopo:** Atherstone Nature Reserve (-24.4162, 26.7503); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm The Downs (-24.14, 30.31); Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Springbok Flats Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45). **Mpumalanga:** Ermelo (-26.51, 29.98). **Northern Cape:** Namaqua National Park (-30.19, 17.55). **Western Cape:** Botrivier (-34.21, 19.2); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in seven protected areas such as Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Bjørn, 1997). Known from both sexes.

After Bjørn (1997)

Argiope lobata female Photo A. Jones

Argiope lobata female Photo P. Webb

NEW RECORD

Argiope tapinobata Bjørn, 1997

COMMON NAME: Long bodied Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Bjørn (1997) from Senegal. The species is known from three countries. However it may possibly be under collected and is suspected to occur in the countries in-between. In South Africa the species is known from Gauteng . Due to its wide geographical range in Africa the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: An *Argiope* with female abdomen almost cylindrical, over twice as long as wide, with very shallow lobes. The specimen from Irene was sampled from grassland mid January 2014.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Senegal, Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Possibly under sampled in southern Africa.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Argiope tapinobata juvenile from Irene Photo Peter Webb

After Bjørn (1997)

Argiope tapinobata female from Namibia Photo L. Bailey

Argiope trifasciata (Forsskål, 1775)

COMMON NAME: Banded Garden Orb-Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Forsskål (1775) as *Aranea trifasciata* and it is found worldwide, except in Europe and Japan. In Africa the species is recorded from three countries. In South Africa the species is known from eight of the nine provinces, including <20 protected areas (EOO= 993 692 km²; AOO= 204 km²; 3-1557 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide global distribution, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes orb-webs in wetlands, open grassland areas and gardens. The webs are usually placed low in shrubby vegetation in any vegetation sturdy enough to bear their weight. The spider hangs at the hub, head down, throughout the day. The species was sampled from all the floral biomes except the Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011), and it was also sampled from crops such as cotton, kenaf, lucerne and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cosmopolitan, found worldwide except in Europe and Japan.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (various localities) (-33.3, 26.52); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **Free State:** Cloccolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58).

Gauteng: Baviaanspoort (-25.67, 28.37); Bon Accord (-25.62, 28.2); Bronkhorstspuit (-25.8, 28.74); Hekpoort (-25.9, 27.61); Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodeplaat (Farm Leeufontein) (-25.63, 28.34). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Banga Nek, Kosi Bay (-27.09, 32.84), Mapelane Nature Reserve (-28.39, 32.42); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Kwambonambi Plantation (-28.63, 32.21); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

Limpopo: Farm Elandsberg, between Warmbath /Thabazimbi (-24.73, 27.72); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Londolozi Game Reserve (-24.86, 31.53); Maasstroom (-22.75, 28.43); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Potgietersrus/Mokopane (-24.17, 29.00); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Blyde River Canyon Nature Reserve (-24.58, 30.82); Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Klingbiel Nature Reserve (-25.09, 30.46);

Argiope trifasciata female in web from Mpetsane Photo A. Jones

Argiope trifasciata Photo J. van Zyl

Argiope trifasciata female Photo J. Tribe

Argiope trifasciata (continued)

Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Machadodorp (-25.66, 30.26); Oudestad Research Station (-25.16, 29.39); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78). **North-West:** Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Magaliesberg (-20.97, 31.65); Olifantsnekdam (-25.8, 27.25). **Western Cape:** Brackenfeld Nature Reserve (-33.9, 18.72); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (Hermanus) (-34.86, 19.34); Cape of Good Hope Nature Reserve (-34.24, 18.41); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Sampled from 14 protected areas such as Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Bjørn 1997). Known from both sexes.

Argiope trifasciata female with egg sac
Photo L. Oates

Argiope trifasciata female ventral view Photo J vd Walt

Argiope trifasciata female with small male in web Photo W. Schmidt

Argiope trifasciata female Photo L. Oates

GENUS *BIJOARANEUS* Tanikawa, Yamasaki & Petcharad, 2021

Five species of *Bijoaraneus* are known with only one known from the Afrotropical Region (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: The Japanese word “Bijo” means beautiful lady

TYPE SPECIES: *Bijoaraneus mitificus* (Simon, 1886)

MORPHOLOGY: Median ocular area wider anteriorly than posteriorly. Abdomen oval, longer than wide. Epigynal scape short, well sclerotized, inflexible; without differentiation between median plate and lateral lamella. Male palp without terminal apophysis, or small and not reaching conductor. Male palpal femur basally with tubercle, tibia with 2 macrosetae. Male endite with lateral tooth. Male coxa I with ventral hook, and dorsal tubercle, femur II with groove, femur II with a row of ventral spines .

LIFESTYLE: It is an orb-web spider. Web with a free sector, silk yellow, with signal line lead to retreat made by living leaf and silk .

TAXONOMY: One species known from South Africa.

Bijoaraneus legonensis female Photo P. Webb

B. legonensis female in silk retreat Photo H. Heron

Bijoaraneus legonensis Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979

COMMON NAME: Bum-Eyed Hairy Field Spiders

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Ghana by Grasshoff & Edmunds (1979), based on both sexes. The species is known only from Ghana and South Africa. It is however suspected to be under collected and to occur in the countries in-between. In South Africa it is known from five provinces (EOO= 549 690 km²; AOO=56 km²; 7-1402 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: It is an orb-web spider. Heron (2017) made some observations on the web building behaviour of the species at Malvern, Queensburgh in KwaZulu-Natal. The spider was found in a small, near-vertical, incomplete yellow orb-web with a diameter of *circa* 13 cm, approximately 1.5 m from the ground on the west-facing side of a tree that was shaded until mid-afternoon. A later web had a diameter of 14 cm. A wedge-shaped section of the upper portion of the web, facing a silken leaf retreat, was missing, and the central hub area was linked to the spider in its retreat by a line – thus confirming the observations of Grasshoff & Edmunds (1979: 306). A silken retreat consisting of whitish threads had been constructed in an adjacent upwardly-folded leaf. The threads were attached to the leaf margins, measured *circa* 15 x 8 mm, and the enclosed spider could be easily observed inverted, hanging within the structure, and facing towards the orb-web. When in danger, the spider tilts its abdomen upwards, showing a row of four dark spots. The purpose of the display was presumed to be defensive and Heron (2017) speculated that the spots were possibly serving two purposes: to draw attention away from the head by presenting a pattern reminiscent of eyes, and to possibly suggest the “face” of a predator. From the size and arrangement, the pattern appeared reminiscent of the eyes of a salticid spider. The species is not very common and was sampled from the Fynbos, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Forest, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ghana, Thailand and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Katberg (-32.78, 26.62); Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.9). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Hilton (-29.56, 30.3); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell’s Gate(-28, 32.48); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Kosi Bay Nature (-26.93, 32.87).

Epigyne after Grasshoff & Edmunds (1979),

Bijoaraneus legonensis female Photo P. Webb

B. legonensis female in retreat Photos H. Heron

***Bijoaraneus legonensis* Grasshoff & Edmunds, 1979**

Limpopo: Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Entabeni Forest (-23.00, 30.23); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve Horsefield (-23.038, 29.442); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Woodbush (-23.78, 30.07); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Mpumalanga:** Nelshoogte Forest Reserve (-25.83, 30.83). **Western Cape:** Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.87, 22.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Recorded in 10 protected areas such as Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa et al. 2010; Foord et al. 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Female in retreat Photo N. Larsen

Female in retreat Photo P. Webb

Female in retreat Photo J. Roff

GENUS CAEROSTRIS Thorell, 1868

The genus is represented by 18 species. Four species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Bark Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Caerostris mitralis* (Vinson, 1863)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 20-25 mm, male 5-6 mm. *Caerostris*, known as bark spiders, are greyish brown with horny or leathery protuberances on their carapace and abdomen, resembling bark. The carapace in the upper cephalic region has a transversal row of four conical protuberances. The sternum variable, in some species covered with white setae in other black. The abdomen is round oval and the dorsal plane varies in shape between species or even in the same species. The tubercles resemble bark structure. The abdomen venter also variable with four, two or no white spots. The legs are provided with rows of long setae that fit snugly around the body when resting. In some species femur IV with spatulate to slender setae. The males are rare and resemble the female but are much smaller in size.

LIFESTYLE: They are known as bark spiders and are typically brown in colour, which, together with abdominal tubercles of varying shapes and sizes, provide effective camouflage to the spiders when at rest on bark (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Den Berg 2010).

Caerostris construct large, complete vertical orb-webs, with many radii and viscid spirals. The bridge lines, which typically attach to vegetation and form the basis for the construction of the web, can even span roads and may be several meters across. The orb-web is made between trees, usually when the sun set, and is removed early in the morning. However in cloudy days the webs are not removed. The bridge line is usually left intact and used again. The spiders rest during the day on the bark of the tree to which the bridge line is attached.

TAXONOMY: The *Caerostris* of the Afrotropical region was revised by Grasshoff (1984).

Caerostris sp. from Wakefield Photo P. Webb *C. sexcupidata* from Aardvark NR Photo P. Webb

From Tokai –sternum, 3 spots

From Pretoria –sternum, 3 spots

From Randburg – Only sternum spot

From Kloof – four spots

From Nylstroom – two long spots

From Stellenbosch no white spots

Caerostris corticosa Pocock, 1902

COMMON NAME: Bare Legged Bark Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic species described from Botswana by Pocock (1902), based only on a female specimen. It has been collected from three other African countries. In South Africa the species is known from eight of the nine provinces, including <5 protected areas (EEO= 961 417 km²; AOO= 64 km²; 7-1303 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The web is made between shrubs and trees, usually at sunset. The spider hangs head-down in the middle of the orb-web. During the day, the spiders rest on thick branches close to the attachment lines of their webs, and their brown or grey colouration provides effective camouflage on bark and lichens (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013). Sampled from five biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (Klipfontein) (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Estcourt (-29.0, 29.87); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04). **Northern Cape:** Honde-klipbaai (-30.31, 17.28). **North West:** Vryburg (-26.95, 24.73). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Kleinmond (-34.33, 19.02); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Grootbrakrivier Kouma Fynbos Eco Trial (-34.03, 22.22); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.87, 22.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Mkuzi Game Reserve, Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989) and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Grasshoff 1984). Identification of male is still problematic. Female recognized by the ventral surface of the abdomen being black or with two white spots, the sternum covered with dense white setae and the posterior side of the femur IV bearing slender undifferentiated hairs. Species closely resembling *C. sexcuspidata*, in colour and general characters.

Caerostris corticosa female Photo I. Anderson

After Grasshoff (1984)

C. corticosa female from Tokai dorsal and ventral view Photo J. Blackshaw

Caerostris corticosa female from Outeniqua NR Photo P. Meyer

Caerostris sexcupidata (Fabricius, 1793)

COMMON NAME: Horned Bark Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Fabricius (1793) as *Aranea sexcupidata*. It occurs throughout Africa. In South Africa the species is known from all nine provinces (EOO= 934 076 km²; AOO= 324 km²; 1-2785 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical distribution, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species builds large orb-webs, usually between trees. They rest on tree bark during the day. The species was also sampled from various crops: apple, citrus, pine plantations and tomatoes. During 1995, spiders were sampled from the herbaceous layer of coastal dune forests at Richards Bay, KwaZulu-Natal. This took place northeast of Richards Bay where a local mining company, Richards Bay Minerals (RBM), began the extraction of minerals from coastal sand dunes in 1976. Four stands of rehabilitating dune forest (2-, 8-, 12- & 16-year old) were sampled as well as one stand in a mature forest (100-years). *Caerostris sexcupidata* with 333 specimens was the most abundant Araneidae species sampled over a period of two months. Their webs were very abundant, especially in the 2-year (66 spiders); 8-year stands (175 spiders), and 12-year stands (88 spiders) while it was absent from the 16-year old stand and only 3 were sampled in the 100-year old forest. Webs frequently abutting one another and in the dense young forest the webs were frequently not removed during the day (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wassenaar 2006). Yates (1968) studied this species in a garden in KwaZulu-Natal and found that the same individual will either remove its web early in the morning or remain in the web throughout the day.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Boesmansriviermond (-33.69, 26.64); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Fort Brown Kudu Reserve (-33.13, 26.62); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kasouga Mouth (-33.63, 26.43); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Kologha Forest Reserve (-32.31, 27.21); Komga (-32.58, 27.9); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Queenstown (Farm Rookwood) (-32.08, 26.59); Silaka Nature Reserve (-31.62, 29.49). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg (Blairgowrie) (-26.1, 28); Maraisburg (-26.11, 27.56); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92).

After Grasshoff (1984)

Caerostris sexcupidata male Photo P. Webb

Caerostris sexcupidata female from Aardvark Nature Reserve Photo P. Webb

Caerostris sexcupidata female from Goukamma NR Photo F. Jordaan

Caerostris sexcuspidata (continue)

KwaZulu-Natal: Amanzimtoti (-30.04, 30.88); Champagne Castle (-29.08, 29.35); Drummond (-29.73, 30.73); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47); Entumeni Nature Reserve (-28.88, 31.29); Giant's Cup Wilderness Reserve (Farm Goschen) (-29.97, 29.46); Greytown (-29.05, 30.6); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ingeli Forest -33.55, 29.42); Inchanga (-29.73, 30.65); Lusikisiki (-31.37, 29.57); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Pongola (Farm Vergeval)(-27.35, 31.61); Port Edward (-31.04, 30.21); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Richmond (-29.86, 30.26); Rosetta (-29.3, 29.99); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Van Reenen (-28.37, 29.38); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 30.57); Winkelspruit (-30.08, 30.38). Limpopo: Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Louis Trichard (-23.04, 29.91); Makalali Nature Reserve (24.34, 30.93); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Nylstroom/Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Potgietersrus/ Mokopane (-24.17, 29); Soutpansberg (-31.04, 20.04); Vivo (-23.04, 29.27). **Mpumalanga:** Sabie (Fanie Botha Hiking Trail) (-25.09, 30.69); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Burgersfort (-24.68, 30.31); Dullstroom (-25.42, 30.10); Hazyview (-25.03, 31.12); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Malelane (-25.49, 31.5); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14). Northern Cape: Richmond (-31.4, 23.95); Klein Papkuil farm (-28.48, 23.72). North-West: Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Molopo Nature Reserve (-26.02, 25.5); Olifantsnekdam (-25.8, 27.25); Rooijkoppies (-25.58, 27.77). **Western Cape:** Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Swellendam (-34.02, 20.42); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Kommetjie (-34.16, 18.34); Ladismith (-33.5, 21.26); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (Moordkuil) (-33.92, 22.11); Stellenbosch (-33.94, 18.86); Newlands Forest (-33.91, 18.42); Saasveld Forest Station (-33.95, 22.53); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52); Table Mountain National Park: Table Mountain (-33.82, 18.48), Silvermine Forest Station (-34.1, 18.4); Wildcliff Nature Reserve (-34.2, 21.07).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in more than 20 protected. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised (Grasshoff 1984). Known from both sexes.

Caerostris sexcuspidata female Photo J. Richard

Caerostris sexcuspidata female Photo P. Webb

Caerostris sexcuspidata female (without spots) in web Photo N. Larsen

Caerostris tinamaze Gregorič, 2015

COMMON NAME: Gregoric's Bark Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: VU B1ab(iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Gregorič (2015) by from Entabeni State Forest. The species is known only from the type locality, an area which is surrounded by habitats transformed by silviculture. (EOO=0 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 1362 m a.s.l.). The species is possibly under sampled or more specimens might be housed in collections that have not been correctly identified. Due to the species having a small distribution range (< 20000 km²) it is regarded as Vulnerable under the B criterion.

LIFESTYLE: The species builds large orb-webs, usually between trees. The examined specimens inhabited an afro-montane forest fragment in a pine plantation in the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Entabeni State Forest (-22.99197, 30.25703).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the male and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Caerostris tinamaze after Gregorič et al (2015).

Caerostris vicina (Blackwall, 1866)

COMMON NAME: Rugose Bark Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in by Blackwall (1866) as *Eurysoma vicina* and known from several countries throughout Africa. In South Africa the species is known from three provinces including several protected areas (EOO= 152 684 km²; AOO= 52 km²; 20-893 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: At Pongola the large *C. vicini* was observed catching prey in a large orb-web (1.0-1.5 m in diameter) during the night. The web was removed early in the morning, with only a strong bridge line remaining between trees during the day when the female retreated to a branch and, with the legs arranged neatly around the body, blended in well with the surroundings (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997). Sampled from the Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa. Recorded from Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Black Rock (-32.02, 29.1). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7); Muden (-28.96, 30.39); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval)(-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ubombo (-27.56, 32.08); Weenen Nature Reserve (-28.84, 30.07); Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Tshulu Camp (Venda) (-22.5798, 30.8086).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Lake Sibaya; Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Tembe Elephant Park; Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Weenen Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Grasshoff (1984). Known from both sexes. In the female the carapace is greyish brown with tubercles in eye region. Abdomen is dorsally flattened with small tubercles; ventrally without distinct white spots. Legs are the same colour as carapace; femur IV with spatulate setae on posterior edge.

Caerostris vicina female Photo E. vd Walt

Caerostris vicina female from Swaziland Photo K. Braun

Caerostris vicina female from fynbos Photo SANSA VM

After Grasshoff (1984)

NEW?

GENUS CHORIZOPES O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871

This genus includes 26 described species and has a wide Indomalayan distribution, with particularly rich faunas described from India and China, and three species known from Madagascar.

COMMON NAMES: Chorizopes Orb-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Chorizopes frontalis* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871.

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace gibbous; anteriorly enlarged; lateral eyes sessile and separated from the median eyes. Abdomen has two large anterior lobes, and a posterior group of four tubercles (one pair of lateral tubercles and two vertically arranged caudal tubercles). Legs the posterior coxae are separated from each other by 2/3 of their diameters.

LIFESTYLE: Apparently they lack capture webs despite being listed within the orb-weaving family Araneidae. Spiders of the genus *Chorizopes* have been observed to prey on other orb-weavers, provoking them from the periphery of the web and attacking the web's occupant when it investigate s (Eberhard 1982).

LOCALITIES IN SOUTH AFRICA: Ophathe Game Reserve; Richards Bay; Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve; Entabeni State Forest

Emerit, 1997

RICHARDSBAY

LEKGALAMEETSE NR

ENTABENI

After Emerit (1997)

NEW ?

GENUS CHORIZOPESOIDES Mi & Wang, 2018

COMMON NAMES: Chorizopesoides Orb-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Chorizopesoides wulingensis* Yin, Wang & Xie, 2018

MORPHOLOGY: The genus is similar to *Chorizopes* species in having an elevated thoracic region, but can be easily distinguished from *Chorizopes* by: (1) abdomen having three pairs of lateral tubercles and three vertically arranged caudal tubercles (2) teeth of chelicerae serrated and separately arranged (3) terminal apophysis absent (4) paracymbium digitiform (5) epigyne having a short scape (absent in *Chorizopes*). Abdomen longer than wide, with three pairs of lateral tubercles and three vertically arranged caudal tubercles. Eyes with anterior median eyes close together with posterior median eyes wider apart; median ocular quadrangle narrower anteriorly; lateral eyes close together wide apart from the median eyes.

LIFESTYLE: Build vertical orb-webs with about 15 cm diameter among shrubs (Mi & Wang, 2018).

TAXONOMY: In South Africa specimens have been sampled that very closely resemble this genus.

LOCALITIES IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Opathe Nature Reserve; Richards bay; Ndumo Game Reserve, Tembe Elephant park.

Female from Tembe Elephant Park Photo R. Steenkamp

Legalameetse NR

Ndumo Game Reserve Photos L. de Beer (son)

Chorizopesoides orientalis after Mi & Wang, 2018).

GENUS *CLADOMELEA* Simon, 1895

Four species of *Cladomelea* are known only from the Afrotropical Region and three are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). More species have been collected that are new to science but still they still need to be described.

COMMON NAMES: African Bolas Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cladomelea longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL female 14-17 mm, male 5-7 mm. These small to medium spiders vary in colour and are recognised by the strong erect tubercles arranged in a row on the carapace. The shape and colour of the abdomen varies and some species are decorated with tubercles and strong setae. The front legs are longer than the rest and possess a dense layer of long thin setae. Male differs from female in size and shape (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Leroy et al. 1998; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2019).

LIFESTYLE: Bolas spiders are nocturnal and construct modified orb-webs that are reduced to a strand of silk that terminates in one to three sticky droplets referred to as a bolas. The silk thread is held by one of the second pair of legs, while the spider hangs from a trapeze line constructed in foliage using the fourth pair of legs. These spiders utilise chemical mimicry by producing a compound that is similar to the mating attractant produced by female moths. When male moths approach the source of the “pheromone”, the changes in the air currents and moth’s wing vibrations alert the spider to the presence of prey nearby. They then swing the bolas rapidly until it makes contact with the flying moth, which is quickly drawn in towards the spider as it reels in the thread. The spiders usually rest in a retreat in foliage close to the trapeze line. The egg sacs are round, brown, and attached to twigs close to the trapeze line. Each egg sac may contain 150–200 eggs.

TAXONOMY: The four known species are well documented.

Cladomelea longipes female Photo

Cladomelea akermani female Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea debeeri female in action Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea akermani female Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea akermani Hewitt, 1923

COMMON NAME: Akerman's Bolas Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: VU B1ab(iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Hewitt (1923) from Pietermaritzburg based on a female. The male was described in 1998 from Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve. The species is known from a few localities including one protected area (EOO= 494 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 652-1245 m a.s.l.). Although the species is known from a restricted area, it is likely to be under collected and more locations are suspected to occur. There is ongoing decline of its grassland habitat due to crop cultivation, forestry plantations and urban development. The species is listed as Vulnerable under the B criterion.

LIFESTYLE: The spider constructs a reduced orb-web consisting of a bolas line used to catch moths at night. *Cladomelea akermani* is found in open grasslands, both in short grasses such as *Themeda triandra* which grows to about 40 cm, and very tall grasses such as giant turpentine grass, *Cymbopogon validus*, which grows over 2 m in height. So far, adults have only been found on grasses and not on other plants. Adult female *C. akermani* are found towards the end of the summer (March), and into autumn. The egg sacs are attached to grass stems (Leroy et al. 1998). The species is known from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.2); Muden (-28.96, 30.39).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve. Threatened by habitat loss to crop cultivation, forest plantations and urban development, particularly around Pietermaritzburg. More sampling needed determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Leroy et al. (1998) with description of the male. Known from both sexes.

Cladomelea akermani female Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea akermani female and small male Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea akermani female with eggs Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004

COMMON NAME: Debeer's Bolas Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: VU B1ab(iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2004), from the type locality Pietermaritzburg. It is known from two localities in KwaZulu-Natal (EOO= 0 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 722-1150 m a.s.l.). Although the species is known from a restricted area, it is likely to be under collected and more locations are suspected to occur. There is ongoing decline of its grassland habitat due to crop cultivation, forestry plantations and urban development. Due to the species having a small distribution range (< 20 000 km²) it is regarded as Vulnerable.

LIFESTYLE: The spider constructs a bolas-line consisting of two to three silk threads, with two to three sticky droplets at the free end. The spider uses the second pair of legs to whirl the bolas-line. Whirling is done at short, erratic intervals of two to five minutes. The spider makes its retreat in a plant about 1.8 m above the soil surface. The species is found in vegetation in the Sub-Escarpment Savanna, but also occurs in suburban gardens. The spider constructs a bolas line used to catch moths at night (Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2004; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2019).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa .

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the male and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female. Identification of male is still problematic.

Cladomelea debeeri female in action
Photo J. Roff

Cladomelea debeeri female Photo J. Roff

Epigyne after Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman (2004)

Cladomelea longipes (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877)

COMMON NAME: Pink Bolas Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by O. Pickard-Cambridge (1877) from Angola. It is known from four African countries. In South Africa it has been recorded from the Limpopo Province. Due to the species having a wide distribution range in Africa it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The spider constructs a reduced orb-web consisting of a bolas line used to catch moths at night. The egg cocoon constructed by *C. longipes* differs from that of other known *Cladomelea* species. The female eventually constructed four egg sacs that were observed suspended 0.5 to 1.9 metres above the ground. The incubation period is about 40 days. The spiderlings (>100) emerged and stay together for up to 36 hours after hatching. During breezier days they left the hatching site quicker. Ballooning was observed when few lift off with the breeze, attached to a length of silk.

The mating process of *Cladomelea* spp. has never been recorded. A very interesting observation was made when the small male was observed sitting on the epigyne of the female on some of the photographs. The white spot on the abdomen of the male was clearly visible, indicating that he sits with his venter pressed against her epigyne. He stayed there for a few days, even while she was feeding (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Odendaal (2020)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: The World Spider Catalog gave the type locality as Congo. Pickard-Cambridge (1877) gave the type locality as the banks of the river Coanza, West Africa. This could be a misspelling of the river Quanza, an important river in Angola. Also known from Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Zimbabwe and South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord 2019; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Odendaal 2020).

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Klaserie (-24.55, 31.02).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to collect the male and determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only the female is known.

Cladomelea longipes female from Harare Photo M. Cumming

Cladomelea longipes female from Klaserie Photo K. Wiesler

C. longipes egg sacs Photo T. Odendaal

Cladomelea longipes female Photo T. Odendaal

GENUS *CLITAE TRA* Simon, 1889

Clitaetra is represented by six species of which five are known from the Afrotropical region. The genus was transferred from Tetragnathidae to Nephilidae by Kuntner (2006) and then transferred from Nephilidae to Araneidae by Dimitrov et al. (2017).

COMMON NAMES: Tree Orb-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Clitaetra episinoides* Simon, 1889

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females 5.7–9.9 mm, males 2.8–3.6 mm. Female carapace and chelicerae yellow-grey; sternum yellow, with irregular white patches along middle, with four pairs of sternal slit sensilla. Abdomen pentagonal, dorsoventrally flattened, with five pairs of dorsomedian apodemes; dorsum with grey, brown and white pattern; venter with broad white median stripe extending from epigastric fold to spinnerets, broken white pattern around spinnerets. Legs whitish-yellow, with dark brown spine-sockets and spines; tarsi brown. Male with sternum light brown; both eye rows recurved. Abdomen oval, with three pairs of dorsal apodemes; scutum present, dark brown, with white frontal band; venter brown, dark grey, caudally with three pairs of white dots around spinnerets.

LIFESTYLE: *Clitaetra irenae* is abundant in sand forests, riparian/floodplain forests and closed-canopy woodlands of the coastal plain of northern KwaZulu-Natal. The spiders typically spin their elongated orb-webs over tree trunks, or even on rock outcrops or on wooden walls. The webs could be described as ladder-webs. They are built more or less vertically, are elongated with parallel vertical sides and their 'spirals' run parallel. The webs are typically built within tree trunk depressions or concave sections. The hub of the orb is reinforced with fine silk mesh. The spider rests at the hub, typically with prey remains suspended above the hub (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Kuntner 2006).

TAXONOMY: Revised by Kuntner (2006).

Clitaetra irenae female in web Photo R. Tippett

Clitaetra irenae Kuntner, 2006

COMMON NAME: Irene's Tree Orb-web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Kuntner (2006) from iSimangaliso Wetland Park. The species was also sampled from Malawi. In South Africa it is mainly recorded from KwaZulu-Natal (EOO=3 401 km²; AOO= 24 km²; 3-91 m a.s.l.). Due to wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The spiders spin orb-webs on tree trunks, or rock outcrop and wooden walls. The webs are typically built within tree trunk depressions such that the clearance between the web and the tree is greatest at the hub (typically 2–4 cm in female webs). The hub of the orb is reinforced with a fine silk mesh. The spider rests at the hub, typically with prey remains suspended above the hub. The webs of adult females are eccentric, the lower portion being larger than the upper. They build webs at night and in the early morning hours, sometimes only partially renewing the old web (typically, the hub and an orb sector are retained and may only be reinforced) (Kuntner 2006).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Malawi, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Gate - 28.1, 32.45); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Camp -27.58, 32.67); Sodwana Bay National Park, Mgoboseleni Trail (-27.4, 32.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Phinda Game Reserve (Ntabankosi Mountains) (-27.72, 32.38); Tembe Elephant Park (Ngobozana sand forest) (-26.94, 32.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following reserves: Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Phinda Game Reserve and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Clitaetra irenae Photo C. Haddad

Clitaetra irenae female in web Photo C. Haddad

GENUS *CYCLOSA* Menge, 1866

The genus *Cyclosa* is known from 174 species and subspecies with a wide distribution. Only three cosmopolitan species are known from South Africa

COMMON NAMES: Garbage-Line Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cyclosa conica* (Pallas, 1772)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females 5–7 mm, male 4–6 mm. Distinct sexual dimorphism in colour and size; male much smaller than female. In most species female body elongate. Body mottled, varies from brown to greyish-black, abdomen decorated with silvery spots or patterns; legs banded; eyes 8 in 2 rows (4:4); abdomen longer than wide and overhanging the carapace; decorated with tubercles; in female, blunt in male. Legs median length (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van den Berg 2010).

LIFESTYLE: They make a complete vertical, closely-woven orb-web in vegetation, about one metre above the ground. The distinguishing character of the web is the vertical stabilimentum, in line with the hub. The spider strings together dead bodies of prey and other debris on the stabilimentum. The spider hides in this debris as a defense against predators. A common species frequently found in sweep-net and beating samples from all of the biomes and sometimes in agroecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2013).

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Cyclosa sp. web and female in web Photo: A. Jones

Cyclosa insulana female in web Photo H. Mitchell

Cyclosa elongata (Lawrence, 1947)

COMMON NAME: Long-Tailed Garbage-Line Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic. The species is known from several localities from four provinces (EOO= 461 847 km²; AOO= 92 km²; 4-1519 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species makes a vertical orb-web with a stabilimentum of prey remains, as do species of *Cyclosa*. The species is known from four biomes. It was also sampled from citrus and pistachio orchards, and cotton fields.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Stanford Hill, Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Island (-28.1, 32.45), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.70); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); New Agatha Forest (-24.03, 30.08); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Mogalakwena Nature Reserve, Farm Nooitgedacht(-22.7649, 28.7078). **Mpumalanga:** Hectorspruit (-25.43, 31.68); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-24.99, 31.593).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in 12 protected areas. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Species originally described as a member of the *Nemoscolus* genus, but it was transferred to the *Cyclosa* (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010). Known only from the female.

Nemoscolus elongate female in web Photo J. Munton

Nemoscolus elongata female Photo P. Webb

Nemoscolus elongate Photo J. Munton

Epigyne ASD

Cyclosa insulana (Costa, 1834)

COMMON NAME: Insulana Garbage-Line Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Costa (1834) as *Epeira insulana* with a wide distribution from the Mediterranean to Japan, India to Papua New Guinea and Australia. In South Africa, the species is very common and known from all nine provinces including >20 protected areas (EOO= 1 089 799 km²; AOO= 260 km²; 4-1593 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make a complete vertical, closely woven orb-web in vegetation, about one metre above the ground. The distinguishing character of the web is the vertical stabilimentum in line with the hub. The spider strings together dead bodies of prey and other debris on this stabilimentum. The spider hides in this debris as a defence against predators. This common species is frequently found in sweep net and beating samples, and has been sampled from all the floral biomes. The species was also recorded from crops such as avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and citrus orchards and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mediterranean to Japan, India to Papua New Guinea and Australia. New record Swaziland and South Africa .

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); East London (-33.01, 27.9); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Keurkloof (Baviaanskloof) (Farm Ferndale) (-33.68, 24.83); Kirkwood (-33.39, 25.43); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Mkambathi Nature Reserve (-31.27, 30.02). **Free State:** Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8). **Gauteng:** Centurion (Irene, Smuts House) (-25.89, 28.23); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (25.8, 28.77); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Wonderboom) (-25.68, 28.2); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Illovo Beach (-30.12, 30.85); iSimangaliso Wetland park: Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Kwa-Mbonambi (-28.6, 32.08); Margate (-30.85, 30.36); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (Sirheni Bushveld camp) (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Mountain Retreat 23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9,

Cyclosa insulana female Photo P. Webb

Epigyne Photo ASD

Cyclosa insulana female Photo H. Mitchell

After Levi (1977)

Cyclosa insulana female Photo H. Mitchell

Cyclosa insulana (continued)

Mpumalanga: Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.06); Hectorspruit (-25.43, 31.68); Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Northern Cape:** Roodewal Forest (-30.45, 17.35). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Cederberg (-32.16, 18.89); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Knysna (-34.02, 22.98); Somerset West (-34.05, 18.83); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); Tokai Forest (-34.05, 18.27).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >30 protected areas such as the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006); Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2013); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Lhuvhondo Mountain Retreat (Foord et al. 2002); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Cyclosa insulana female in web Photo A. Jones

Male and female Photo R. Jocqué

Cyclosa oculata (Walckenaer, 1802)

COMMON NAME: Oculata Garbage-Line Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Walckenaer (1802) as *Aranea oculata*. It has a very wide distribution throughout Europe, Caucasus, Russia (Europe to Far East), Central Asia and China. In South Africa the species is common, known from six provinces and six protected areas (EOO=644 382 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 9-1930 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make a complete vertical, closely woven orb-web in vegetation, about one metre above the ground. The distinguishing character of the web is the stabilimentum in line with the hub. The spider strings together dead bodies of prey and other debris on this stabilimentum. The spider hides in this debris as a defence against predators. This common species is frequently found in beating and sweep net samples. Sampled from four biomes (Foord et al. 2p011). The species was also sampled from citrus, cotton (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999), macadamia (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2001) and potatoes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Europe, Caucasus, Russia (Europe to Far East), Central Asia and China. New South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Kirkwood (-33.39, 25.43). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.2); Farm Wakefield Midlands (-29.28, 29.53). **Limpopo:** Makalali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); **Mpumalanga:** Hectorspruit (-25.43, 31.68); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Schagen (-25.43, 30.8); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve, Makalali Nature Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2001), Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Cyclosa oculata female Photo P. Webb

Cyclosa oculata male Photo P. Webb

Cyclosa oculata female from Aardvark Photo P. Webb

Cyclosa oculata female Photo P. Webb from Kloof

After Levi (1977)

Cyclosa spp. undetermined species

First record of *Cyclosa octotuberculata* from southern Africa a species only known from China, Korea, Taiwan, Japan. Observation made by Anka Eichhoff from Namibia

Cyclosa conica ? From Pinetown Photo J. van Zyl

Cyclosa sp. From Kuruman Photo R. Steenkamp

Spider from Plettenberg bay photograph by Claire Hamilton

GENUS *CYPHALONOTUS* Simon, 1895

The genus *Cyphalonotus* is known from seven species with three species known from Africa and Madagascar (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Cyphalonotus Twig Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cyphalonotus larvatus* (Simon, 1881)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females and males 5–8 mm long but 10 mm high. Female: carapace cryptic greyish-brown, hairy; eyes in *Cyphalonotus* are slightly separated on a forward protruding eye tubercle and both lateral eyes are close together at the base of the eye tubercle. This differs from *Polys*, where the posterior lateral eyes are wide apart. Abdomen triangular in lateral view, dorsal part with large hump; abdomen same colour as carapace; abdomen much higher than wide, having numerous antero-dorsal lobes and processes; posterior vertical face very extensive, with short processes. Legs femora without ventral spines; legs long, leg III shortest (Dippenaar- Schoeman 2014; Dippenaar- Schoeman & Haddad 2014).

LIFESTYLE: *Cyphalonotus* is widely distributed in the eastern parts of the Afrotropical Region, but little is known about its biology. Archer (1965) suggested that this genus belongs to the group that does not construct a formal web but Lawrence (1952) found specimen in webs on shrubs as well as specimens without webs among damp leaves. In Irene (Webb 2013) photographed *Cyphalonotus larvatus* after dark in a large orb-web. The spider hangs in the centre with the legs spread out. When disturbed, the legs, with the web are pulled together. The web is taken down during the day, when they rest on bark with the legs protruding into the air and arranged around the body (Dippenaar- Schoeman et al. 2013). Only one species has been recorded in South Africa but there might be more. Field data indicate that the genus have been collected in savanna grassland as well as from trees such as *Vachellia tortilis*. In the Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) the species was sampled from *Grewia flavescens* and *Ochna pulchra* trees.

TAXONOMY: Not revised. There are more undescribed species from South Africa.

Cyphalonotus larvatus female in web at night from Irene Photo P. Webb

Cyphalonotus larvatus (Simon, 1881)

COMMON NAME: Larvatus Twig Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Zanzibar by Simon (1881) as *Polys larvata*. It has a wide distribution through Africa. In South Africa the species is known from seven provinces (EOO= 655 148 km²; AOO=176 km²; 4-1618 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as being Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: After dark they weave a large orb-web. The spider hangs in the centre with the legs spread out. When disturbed the legs are pulled together. The web is taken down in day time when the spider rest on bark with the legs sticking up in the air and arranged around the body. The species was sampled from the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). It has also been sampled from crops such as: avocado (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005), citrus and macadamia orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2001; 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa and Zanzibar.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72);Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis. (-34.192, 24.713). **Free State:** Erfenisdam Nature reserve (-28.50, 26.80); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.78, 28.2); Roodepoort (-32.026, 27.513). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Lake St. Lucia (-28, 32.48); Gingindlovu (-29.02, 31.59); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.10, 30.26); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Maasstroom (-22.75, 28.43); Makalali Nature Reserve (24.34, 30.93); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Venetia Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.33); Roodewal Forest (-23.0211, 30.0326). **Mpumalanga:** Glenwood (-25.48, 30.92); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96). **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Weltevrede farm near Vryburg (-27.41, 24.51).

Cyphalonotus larvatus Photo L. Oates

Male palp C. Haddad

Epigyne after Archer (1951).

Cyphalonotus larvatus female Photo P. Webb

Cyphalonotus larvatus (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >23 protected areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009) and Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

C. larvatus female from Tswaing Crater NR Photo P. Webb

Female from Groenkloof NR Photo P. Webb

Female from KZN Photo B. Blake

Cyphalonotus larvatus female from Addo Photo L. Wiese

Male anterior view Photo B. Blake

GENUS *CYRTARACHNE* Thorell, 1868

The genus described by Thorell (1868) is known from 55 species and sub species and eight species are recorded from the Afrotropical region (World Spider Catalog 2020). Presently only one species know from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Bird Dropping araneid Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cyrtarachne grubei* (Keyserling, 1864)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females 5–8 mm, males 2–3 mm. Female carapace brown; shiny; carapace convex and simple; ocular quadrangle slightly wider than long, lateral eyes contiguous. Abdomen large, triangular, wider than long, decorated with horizontal bands of white and brown centrally, with paired sigilla; dorsum shiny, appearing hard and shell-like. Legs short, integument leathery with coloured bands and patches. Male differs from female, much smaller (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones 2008).

LIFESTYLE: They construct “spanning thread-webs”, a basic orb-web, but the web diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from that of typical orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets. Each of the short threads between the radii is known as a spanning thread, and is unique in that it breaks when prey comes into contact with it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the hub of the web to feed. During the day the spider rests on close-by vegetation mimicking bird-droppings. They have been sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

TAXONOMY: Not revised.

Cyrtarachne ixodooides female Photo S. Adams

Cyrtarachne ixodooides female Photo S. Adams

Cyrtarachne ixodooides female Photo A Jones

Cyrtarachne ixodooides female Photo J. van Zyl

Cyrtarachne ixoides (Simon, 1870)

COMMON NAME: Bird dropping araneid spiders

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Simon (1870) as *Peltosoma ixoides* with a wide global distribution. It has been recorded from the Mediterranean basin to Georgia and Madagascar. It is not that common in South Africa and is presently known from four provinces (EOO= 251 166 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 16-1656 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide distribution it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct “spanning thread-webs”, a basic orb-web, but the web diameter, sticky spiral spacing and viscid thread diameter differ from that of typical orb-webs. The viscid threads are studded with large droplets. Each of the short threads between the radii is known as a spanning thread, and is unique in that it breaks when prey comes into contact with it. The prey flies into the web, gets stuck to a viscid thread, the thread breaks, and the spider pulls the prey up to the hub of the web to feed. During the day the spider rests on close-by vegetation mimicking bird-droppings (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jones 2008; Emerit 2000).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mediterranean basin to Georgia, and in Madagascar. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bathurst (-33.50, 26.84); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Grahamstown (-33.30, 26.52); Cape St. Francis Bay (-34.13, 24.84). **Free State:** Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan)(-28.8, 27.65). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Isandlwane Nature Reserve (-28.359, 30.640). **Western Cape:** Mosselbay (-34.18, 22.12).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Dukuduku Forest; Isandlwane Nature Reserve and Mpetsane Conservation Estate. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Cyrtarachne ixodoides female Photo S. Adams

Cyrtarachne ixodoides spanning thread web Photo A. Jones

Cyrtarachne ixodoides female ventral view Photo A. Jones

Epigyne ASD

GENUS *CYRTOPHORA* Simon, 1864

The genus is represented by 53 species and subspecies and only two species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Tropical Tent Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cyrtophora citricola* (Forsskål, 1775)

MORPHOLOGY: Size: TL females 12–18 mm, males 3–5 mm. Female: carapace almost flat dorsally, with long cephalic region; carapace dark but covered with dense layer of white setae; median ocular quadrangle slightly longer than wide, lateral eyes slightly separated. Abdomen: overhanging carapace; longer than wide, slightly flattened, bearing three pairs of tubercles near edge; abdomen varies in colour from black with white spots to almost creamish-brown. Legs: moderately long and stout, banded. Male much smaller, without abdominal tubercles (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014).

LIFESTYLE: *Cyrtophora* is widely distributed in the world, with the cosmopolitan species *C. citricola* commonly found throughout the Afrotropical Region. It makes a unique modified araneid orb-webs superficially resembling that of the Linyphiidae. There are many hypotheses as to whether the *Cyrtophora* web is the predecessor of the true orbweb or whether it is derived from that of a linyphiid ancestor. The web of *Cyrtophora* consists of a fine-meshed sheet, similar to the enlarged central area of orb-webs, but made of dry silk and arranged horizontally. It is positioned in an irregular support system consisting of silk threads above and below the mesh. The top structure is denser than the bottom structure. The spider hangs upside-down in the centre. Insects flying into the top support system are knocked down and grasped by the spider hence the name 'knock-down trap'. Owing to its complex three-dimensional structure, the web is invariably built between rigid supports provided by, for instance aloes. *Cyrtophora citricola* frequently forms colonial aggregations, but each spider has its own web. A study of subsocial behaviour in *C. citricola* in West Africa showed that capture efficiency is correlated with aggregation size. A selective factor is the ability to utilize insect-abundant habitats not readily available to solitary species. The conspicuousness of large colonies, however increases the incidence of avian predation and kleptoparasitism (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Joqué (1997; Francini et al. 2013).

TAXONOMY: Only two species is known from South Africa.

Cyrtophora citricola Photo P. Webb

Cyrtophora petersi from Malelane Photo: P. Stephen

Typical tropical tent-web of *Cyrtophora* Photo A. Jones

Cyrtophora citricola (Forsskål, 1775)

COMMON NAME: Tropical Tent Web Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A cosmopolitan species described Forsskål (1775) as *Aranea citricola*. It has a very wide distribution throughout subtropical and tropical areas of Asia, Africa and Australia. In South Africa the species is known from all the provinces including >30 protected areas. (EOO=1 256 155 km²; AOO= 380 km²; 5-1842 m a. s.l.). Due to its wide global distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make an adapted orb-web. Tropical tent-web spiders build their fine-meshed, horizontal non-adhesive orb-webs in plants. The web is an adapted orb-web and tent like in appearance. Barrier webs are made above the sheet and flying insects are initially caught in the upper webbing. Many webs can be grouped together. Also found in crops such as: citrus, lemon and pistachio orchards, pine plantations, pistachio, prickly pears and tomatoes. They can sometimes become a problem in orchards due to their abundance and the dense webs (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014; Franzini et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread in subtropical and tropical areas of Asia, Africa, Australia, and in the warm coastal Mediterranean areas of Europe.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Alexandria (-33.65, 26.4); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); East London (Pineapple Research Station) (-33.01, 27.9); Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Gauteng:** Baviaanspoort (-25.67, 28.37); Irene (-25.87, 28.22); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Onderstepoort (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pyramid (-25.35, 28.37); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Rietveldam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Amanzimtoti (-30.04, 30.88); Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Hluhluwe (-28.02, 32.28); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.4, 32.76); Jozini (-27.42, 32.07); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Sungulwane Game Reserve (-28.87, 31.18); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

Cyrtophora citricola female Photos J. van Zyl

Cyrtophora citricola females showing abdominal variations

Epigyne photo ASD

C. citricola female Photo Vida van der Walt

Cyrtophora citricola (continued)

Limpopo: Alma (-24.49, 28.07); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); De Hoek Forest Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Diphuti (-24.38, 30.66); between Warmbath/ Thabazimbi (Farm Elandsberg) (-24.73, 27.72); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Londoloz Game Reserve (-24.86, 31.53); Maasstroom (-22.75, 28.43); Nylstroom/ Modimolle (-24.69, 28.4); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Rochdale farm (-22.54, 29.41); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Welgevonden Nature Reserve (-24.39, 27.78). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Hectorspruit (-25.43, 31.68); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Louw's Creek (-25.79, 31.04); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58); Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82); Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Leeudoringstad (-27.23, 26.23); Makwassie (-27.3, 25.99); Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08); Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Zeerust (-25.53, 26.08). **Northern Cape:** Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park (Urikaruus Camp) (-25.78, 20.39). **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Fish Hoek, Peer Hill (-34.05, 18.35); Hermanus (-34.4, 19.25); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38); Kommetjie (-34.16, 18.34); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Robberg Nature Reserve (-34, 23); Sedgfield (-34.03, 22.81); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.98, 23.52).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >30 protected areas such as: Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); Tembe Elephant Park Haddad et al. 2009); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) etc. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes.

Cyrtophora citricola web Photo Allen Jones

C. citricola female with egg sacs Photo S. Foord

Cyrtophora citricola juvenile webs Photo A.Jones

Cyrtophora petersi Karsch, 1878

COMMON NAME: Peters' Tropical Tent-Web spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Karsch (1878) from Mozambique. The species has recently been recorded for the first time from South Africa. It is possibly under sampled and is expected to be found in more countries. In South Africa it has been recorded from Mpumalanga and KwaZulu-Natal (EOO < 20000 km²). Due to its wide global geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The species builds modified orb-webs known as tent-webs. Females were found resting beneath a dead leaf suspended from the hub of the web in sand forest, with males resting in parts of the tent web. One male was sampled in a citrus orchard. Sampled from the Savanna biome (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2014); Franzini et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA. KwaZulu-Natal: Tembe Elephant Park, Manjwana Picnic Spot (-26.96, 32.41). **Mpumalanga:** Malelane (-25.49, 31.50).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Tembe Elephant Park. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the female. Male identification still a problem it was recently discovered but not yet described.

Cyrtophora petersi from Malelane Photo P. Stephen

Cyrtophora petersi Photo I. Riddell

Cyrtophora petersi dorsal view Photo C. Haddad

Cyrtophora petersi ventral view Photo I. Riddell

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